

Call for Articles (*Volume I, Issue 2*)

The editors of the *Journal of Metaphysical Thought* welcome article submissions for the Journal's second issue. **The thematic focus of Volume I, Issue 2 is "metaphysical healing."** This issue will feature articles focused on many areas of metaphysical or spiritual healing. Articles related to other areas of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) will be considered provided that they also relate in some way to metaphysics.

Examples of metaphysical healing techniques include, but are not limited to:

- Reiki,
- mental/metaphysical healing,
- dowsing,
- Quantum Touch,
- entity identification/removal,
- angel healing,
- crystal healing,
- meditation,
- prayer,
- spiritual sources of "dis-ease,"
- metaphysical aromatherapy,
- ethics of metaphysical healing,
- Akashic records healing, and
- other energy healing modalities.

Please note that as a spiritually-focused publication we are unable to accept articles relating to the diagnosis or prescriptive treatment of any disease or health condition by non-licensed providers. In the United States, this can be considered "practicing medicine" without a license.

For liability reasons, we will not accept articles that promote CAM or spiritual practices in lieu of medical treatment (even if evidence suggests that a given CAM practice is more effective). We will not permit publication of articles recommending practices that could endanger readers or create legal problems for the author(s) and/or the Journal.

Authors writing about CAM modalities must be currently certified practitioners and

able to provide proof of certification. Exceptions to these rules will be made on a case-by-case basis for qualified and currently licensed health providers writing about topics within their specialties. Any research articles focused on human subjects must be approved by the author's Institutional Review Board. This rule does not pertain to case studies, reviews, or perspective articles.

About the Journal

The purpose of the Journal is to promote discourse and information exchange among professional practitioners of metaphysics and New Thought. The focus of this journal is primarily practice with a secondary focus on research.

With an emphasis on practice-based and research-based articles, the Journal publishes peer reviewed practice-based articles, case studies, editorials, original research, "brief" articles, and reviews. All articles will be published online as "open access" – at no cost to authors – and in print. Print volumes are available for individual purchase for a nominal fee.

The Journal of Metaphysical Thought covers a range of disciplines, including metaphysics, consciousness studies, New Thought principles, spirituality, and metaphysical theology.

Article Preparation and Submission

For article preparation instructions, see www.metaphysicalthought.com or email editor@metaphysicalthought.com. Topics in any area of metaphysics, consciousness studies and New Thought pertaining to the issue theme will be considered.

For this issue, submit your first draft by **October 31** to allow ample time for peer review and editing. We anticipate releasing this issue right after Christmas.